

Revisiting Dharma as an Ethical Foundation of the Indian Knowledge System for Education and Leadership

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Abstract:

The Indian Knowledge System (IKS) is a vast, multidimensional reservoir of wisdom encompassing philosophy, ethics, science, aesthetics, and holistic human development. Among its central concepts, *Dharma* stands out as a foundational ethical principle guiding individual conduct, social harmony, and universal order. This paper revisits the concept of Dharma with a specific focus on personal integrity, exploring how these ethical foundations remain profoundly relevant to contemporary society's moral, cultural, and developmental challenges. Drawing from classical texts such as the Vedas, Upanishads and Bhagavad Gita, the paper outlines how Dharma integrates duty, righteousness, and moral responsibility. It analyses the role of personal integrity through frameworks such as *Trikarana Shuddhi* (purity of thought, speech, and action), *Yama–Niyama* (ethical codes of Yoga), and the emphasis on conscience (*antaratma*). The discussion further highlights the practical applications of Dharma-based ethics in modern spheres such as education and leadership, It argues that the revival of Dharma-inspired values can promote holistic development, emotional well-being, moral courage, and social cohesion. The paper concludes by advocating for the integration of IKS-based ethical education and character formation in contemporary institutions as a pathway to cultivating value-based societies.

Keywords: Indian Knowledge System, Dharma, Ethics, Personal Integrity, Holistic Development, Raj dharma, moral courage, Value Education.

Introduction

The most basic and pervasive concept in Indian thought is Dharma (Kohler, 1972,131). The term Dharma is a complicated concept, embracing many differing though related meanings and extending to a wide range of referents. There are different types of dharmas and uses of dharma, that focus on normative features. Though there are many kinds of dharma, they all involve the notion of regulation and are therefore basically

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rules of action. (Kohler, 1972, 131). The normative ordering of anything is said to be its dharma. The King's regulation of his kingdom is his Rajdharma. The regulation of natural elements or things is their dharma (Padarthadharma), the regulation of communities is community dharma (samajadharma) (Kohler, 1972, 131). The rules of life for a particular class of persons in society constitutes varnadharma, the rules of life for a particular period in one's life are known as asramadharma. And the regulation of life according to basic norms that all persons have in common despite differences in age or social class are dharmasadhanadharma or samanyadharma. (Kohler, 1972, 131). The above-mentioned dharma all aim at ordering human actions so that these would facilitate the achievements of certain ends or aims of life. Dharma as a human aim (Purusharthas) is the aim of living in accordance with all various rules that apply to a person, in a particular class, stage in life and simply as a human being. As an aim in life rather than as a rule of conduct, dharma refers to 'being established in dharma' (Kohler, 1972, 131). To become established in dharma it is necessary to develop the habit of observing the relevant particular dharma or moral rules. This is analogous to virtue, for if one aims at virtue, in the sense of living, a virtuous life, then it is necessary to perform virtuous actions as a matter of character.

Purpose and Relevance: to Explore Dharma as a core ethical principle of the Indian Knowledge system and highlight its relevance in education and leadership. The present study aims at showing how Dharma can guide moral decision making, character formation and responsible leadership in contemporary society. Dharma is relevant for addressing ethical challenges, value-based learning and leadership integrity. Dharma as a value offers timeless insights for nurturing socially responsible citizens and ethics leaders in today's changing world.

Research Methodology: The Study has made use of several secondary sources from books, journals and interpreted versions of holy books. It has mostly used interpretative or explanatory hermeneutical qualitative research methods.

Dharma as a normative ethical framework

Dharma is not to be understood as a religious ideal but as a normative ethical framework embedded in the Indian knowledge system. In Darsana, Dharma has its role directly (or by itself) to the final goal of life that is liberation. The Vedas emphasize on ritualistic practices as means to our highest goal. But the Vedas hardly contain any idea of Moksha as the highest goal. (Tiwari, 1998, 106). Heaven, a place of abiding pleasure and rejoicing is taken as the highest goal that is attainable by pleasing gods through ritualistic practices. There is controversy as to whether ritualistic acts can be taken as constituting part of Dharma itself. We may see that

ritualistic acts have their place in dharma even in the system beyond the Vedas. (Tiwari, 1998, 106). For instance, within the scheme of varnasramadharm there is scope for rituals and this dharma have their important place in almost all the Indian system. (Tiwari, 1998, 106). In Mimamsa system, Nityanaimittika karmas, rituals have got an important place and the performance of these karmas is an essential part of one's dharma. In the Indian traditions, Dharma includes certain performances of rituals. From a general understanding of the vedas, rituals appear to have a superior role in that direction (Tiwari, 1998, 107).

Dharma is prescribed by the Vedas. It is considered as a means to the highest good. The sources of Dharma are Rk, Yajus, Sama and Atharva, Smrti, good conduct (Sila) of persons well-versed in them, conduct (Acara) of virtuous persons and satisfaction of the self (Atmanah-tusti). A moral action is approved by conscience, gives satisfaction to the soul (atmatusti) (Sinha, 1999, 111). The means of knowing Dharma is perception, reason and sastras. Instructions of the sages in harmony with prescriptions of the vedas and reason (Tarka) also are the means of knowing it. (Sinha, 1999, 111). Dharma is what is done by persons well versed in the Vedas and always approved by the conscience of virtuous persons. (Sinha, 1999, 111). Acara (customary conduct) is the source of Dharma. (Sinha, 1999, 112). This is the supreme dharma which is in accordance with Sruti and Smrti. It must be followed by the person who intends to realize the highest good. The good in life is not achieved if one deviates from customary conduct (acara), good is achieved by one who observes it. The ethos of the community needs to be observed. Dharma is the cause of happiness and vice is the cause of misery. (Sinha, 1999, 113) wealth and happiness are transient. Dharma alone accompanies the soul to the other world. Dharma or virtue is the permanent excellence of character which is the result of habitual performance of duties. A person should acquire dharma slowly by performing his duties always. (Sinha, 1999, 113), Dharma takes him to heaven quickly and he can avoid suffering in hell with the aid of Dharma. Non-injury is also a great virtue. Dharma should be acquired without causing pain to any creatures. In the Epic of Mahabharata, God is the promulgator of Dharma (Dharmakarta), the protector of Dharma (Dharmagopta) and the embodiment of Dharma (Dharmin). He is the foundation of Dharma and the observer of Dharma. (Sinha, 1999, 122), Dharma is hindered by wealth. Wealth and dharma are hindered by happiness. Mean people regard wealth as the fruit of Dharma, happiness as the fruit of wealth and sensual pleasure as the fruit of desire. Wise person regard purification of mind as the fruit of Dharma, performance of sacrifices as the fruit of wealth, preservation of life as the fruit of desire. Happiness, wealth and dharma ought to be pursued after duly considering their relative strength and consequences. They should be pursued by all with a pure heart (Sinha, 1999, 133). Dharma sustains the social order, protects the people and bring about social cohesion. Dharma is what is approved by virtuous persons everywhere. (Sinha, 1999, 135). Acara is the foundation of dharma. Any good conduct is dharma

and it's characterized by virtuous persons. It is non-injury to all creatures, what is conducive is good, non-injury and preservation of all creatures is Dharma. The goal of mankind or social solidarity is the highest dharma. The conscience of every person is the true test of Dharma.

Applications of Dharma-Based Ethics in Modern Education

In education, Dharma offers a framework for cultivating holistic development rather than limiting learning to cognitive acquisition. The idea of svadharma, for instance, supports pedagogical approaches that respect individual aptitudes and learning trajectories, encouraging educators to facilitate student-specific growth rather than apply uniform expectations. The purusharthas framework can be reframed to import value-based education, connecting knowledge acquisition (Jnana) and Skill development (artha) and ethical responsibility (Dharma) and personal fulfilment (Kama) in balanced proportions. This kind of integrated model is advantageous for curriculum design and student development program. Dharma thus promotes academic integrity, respectful dialogues and community accountability.

Application of Dharma in leadership skills in contemporary society

The concept of Dharma occupies a central place in ancient Hindu thought. In the whole book or parva of Mahabharata namely shantiparva, Bishama describes to King Yudhishtira known as Dharmaraja, the intricacies of Rajdharma. Rajdharma is exalted as the refuge of all living creatures and leads to the realization of not only the three-fold end of life but also to Moksha or spiritual salvation (Suda, 1970, 357). Rajdharma is believed to be the means of controlling the world like the reins controlling horses. (Suda, 1970, 357). If dharma that is observed by the king gets confused, disorder in the world sets in and the kingdom would be plunged in darkness and chaos. When the king abandons his royal dharma, the dharmas of all the four classes of society and of the four ashramas of life also disappear (Suda, 1970, 357). Thus, rajdharma plays a significantly important role in life. So, protection of dharma was regarded as the most important duty of the king and the king himself as the protector of Dharma.

Ramayana also offers a profound guide to leadership, this is illustrated in the form of Rajdharma, the ethical code for leader/ruler. The principles of rajdharma, the ethical code governing kingship, remains remarkably relevant in our contemporary world. Ramayana presents a sophisticated framework for understanding the responsibilities and challenges inherent in leading a society. (Priti Gupta, 2025, 233). The portrayal of leadership, examining how Rama's conduct and decision provide a blue print not for just and effective rule, not just for kinds of the old, but for leaders in all spheres of life. The concept of Rajdharma is not

merely a set of rules but a comprehensive ethical framework that emphasizes the king's duty to uphold dharma (righteousness) , protect his subject, and ensure well-being. It is a philosophy that transcends personal ambition and prioritizes the collective good (Priti Gupta, 2025, 233). Rama's character is an exemplary person for the embodiment of rajdharma. In spite of facing immense personal hardships, he has demonstrated his unwavering commitment to ethical principles. His adherence to truth, his compassion for subjects, and his ability to remain steadfast in the face of adversity make him an ideal role model for all leaders. The principles of dharma, justice and ethical decision making are universal and can guide leaders from any field.

The epic also depicts a hard contrast between Rama's righteous rule and Ravana's reign. The difference highlights the importance of moral leadership and destructive consequences of unchecked power and ego. Ravana's downfall serves as a cautionary tale illustrating the dangers of deviating from Dharma (Priti Gupta, 2025, 233).

The Ramayana's insights into leadership and governance remains relevant in our modern world, often characterized by ethical dilemmas and complex challenges. The Epic's emphasis on dharma, justice and compassion provides a timeless framework for navigating these challenges and building a just and harmonious society. (Priti Gupta, 2025, 233).

The ethical foundation of kingship/leadership:

King Rama as the exemplary figure of Rajdharma: as a king and exemplar of rajdharma, he is an example of ethical code for rulers. Rajdharma is a comprehensive set of duties and virtues expected of a king in ancient Indian texts. He has always prioritized dharma over personal desires even when faced with difficulties and challenges.

Adherence to dharma: his exile is also an exemplary commitment to dharma. His willingness to relinquish his rightful claim to throne and go into exile honours his father's promises this act highlights his dedication to truthfulness and obedience, core tenets of dharma. (Priti Gupta, 2025, 234)

Virtues of Raj dharma: Rama exemplified virtues such as truthfulness, righteousness, compassion and self-control as part of his Raj dharma.

Service to subjects: his interactions with his subjects reflects his duty to serve his people. He treated his subjects with humility and empathy, recognizing their needs and concerns. He views his role as a service rather than a position or power. This fosters trust, loyalty among his people.

In leadership, Dharma based ethics provides a charismatic model for leaders grinding authority in responsibility, moral clarity and service. A dharmic leader functions as a trustee rather than a controller. Aligning decision making with broader social and environmental wellbeing. Rajdharma provides guidance for corporate government practices and conflict resolution mechanisms. The Dharmic virtue of equanimity strengthens leadership, resilience by encouraging non-reactive balanced responses to stress, uncertainty and organizational change. The emphasis on satya (truthfulness) and Ahimsa (non-harm) can enhance ethical communication, reduce toxic workplace cultures and strengthen trust between teams and leaders.

Conclusion

These observations illustrate that Dharma is not merely a metaphysical or cultural concept, but can be understood as a functional ethical system that enables humans in shaping real world practices. By grounding institutional framework in responsibility, interdependence and integrity, Dharma based ethics offers a robust, adaptable model for addressing contemporary challenges in education and leadership.

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